

AI & mitigation scenarios

Exploring climate futures with deep learning

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Glancing forward to view alternative futures for limiting global warming requires understanding complex societal-environmental systems that drive future emissions. Now a study explores the potential, and limits, of deep learning to generate core characteristics of these futures.

Climate change poses serious challenges, demanding robust strategies for long-term emissions reduction. To explore these strategies, the scientific community develops various climate change mitigation scenarios – plausible future pathways that project the transformations needed to meet climate goals¹. These scenarios, often assessed by bodies like the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)², inform crucial climate policy decisions. Traditionally, integrated assessment models (IAMs) have been the principal tools for generating these projections. IAMs are computational tools that use simplified mathematical representations of societal-environmental interactions and integrate assumptions about population, economy, technology and policy³. Writing in *Nature Climate Change*, Peijin Li and colleagues⁴ explore a different approach to IAMs, employing deep learning (DL) – a form of artificial intelligence adept at finding complex patterns in large data – to generate key indicators characterizing these scenarios.

IAMs, while indispensable, face challenges. Generating large ensembles (that is, collections) of scenarios as means to explore uncertainty can be computationally expensive. Furthermore, the resulting scenario ensembles inevitably contain biases and incomplete coverage of the possibility space⁵, a consequence of limitations in both the IAMs themselves and the specific scenario designs envisaged and selected by scientists for exploration⁶. The diversity of IAMs—which may differ significantly in their underlying assumptions and how they represent economies, technologies, and time²—allows for exploring problems from different angles but also introduces model-specific fingerprints (‘idiosyncratic structures’ as Li et al. term it) on the outcomes. This complexity forms the backdrop against which new methods are being sought.

Li and colleagues⁴ enter this space by developing a DL framework trained on the extensive scenario database assessed by the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report, which contains results from numerous IAM studies². Their objective was not to create entirely novel pathways from scratch, but rather to demonstrate whether DL models – specifically generative approaches – can effectively replicate key trends and relationships among variables found within this database. They rigorously tested various DL frameworks, identifying those best suited for capturing core characteristics across different scenario categories (defined by warming levels). Their approach successfully reproduced six key mitigation indicators. Additionally, it replicated a detailed set of variables describing the mix of power sector fuels. This latter capability demonstrates the potential of DL frameworks for capturing sectoral nuances, but importantly enabled the authors to perform specific, albeit very limited, validation checks on the generated data.

The authors are commended for this methodological exploration. Their work serves as an important proof-of-concept. While the initial training of the DL models requires computational time comparable to generating a single IAM *modelled* scenario, the trained DL models can then generate 30,000 *synthetic* scenarios within seconds. Crucially, compared to the hundreds of variables typically included in a full IAM *modelled* scenario, these *synthetic* scenarios reproduce only six key mitigation indicators (plus the detailed power sector fuels variables used for internal consistency checks – i.e. validation). The multi-stage process that they outline, including identifying key drivers, training and confirming the accuracy of different DL models, and performing validation checks, provides a valuable template for future research in this nascent field⁷. As the authors highlight, this capability could be useful for tasks such as rapidly assessing the implications of near-term targets based on patterns learned from long-term scenarios.

However, this approach also gives rise to critical considerations for the scientific community. As Li et al. acknowledge, DL models trained on existing scenario datasets inevitably inherit any limitations and biases present in that data – stemming from both the IAMs used to generate these data and the specific scenario designs originally chosen⁶. While the DL framework replicates observed variable distributions and correlations, the resulting *synthetic* scenarios lack the built-in physical and economic consistency ensured, to an extent, by the detailed processes captured in IAMs. The sector-specific validation performed by the authors is a crucial step, but confirming consistency across the wider system remains a challenge for these purely data-driven outputs. Furthermore, the valuable diversity of insights gained from comparing results across different IAM structures² is obscured when scenarios are generated via a DL model trained on an extensive scenario database.

This leads to fundamental questions about how we interpret and use these ‘synthetic scenarios’, as opposed to ‘modelled scenarios.’ Maintaining this clarity in terminology used is vital as AI tools become more integrated into mitigation research, perhaps eventually leading to hybrid modelling

approaches^{8,9}. Ensuring transparency is crucial for building trust in synthetic data products¹⁰. It is also essential to understand what constitutes adequate vetting and validation for this new type of scenario, beyond statistical replication. The scientific community needs to develop standards for assessing the credibility and appropriate use of such synthetic outputs, ensuring they are not misinterpreted as possessing the same level of detailed processes captured in IAM-modelled scenarios.

Li and colleagues position their work as illustrating the potential for DL to *complement* IAMs, primarily through computational efficiency. Currently, the demonstrated application focuses on replication. Future research, as the authors suggest, might explore whether DL can help expand the scenario space in targeted ways, perhaps generating scenarios tailored to specific questions or incorporating region-specific drivers to address under-representation, moving beyond simply mirroring the training data. However, achieving this without propagating existing biases or generating seemingly plausible but internally inconsistent futures remains an obvious hurdle. Consideration of important aspects such as equity and justice, often not explicitly modelled in IAMs², also remains an open challenge for these new approaches.

In conclusion, Li and colleagues provide a valuable demonstration of the capabilities of DL in the field of mitigation scenarios. Their work highlights the power of these tools for replicating complex datasets efficiently. Yet, as we capitalize on the growing potential of AI in climate science⁷, it is crucial that the community proceeds with caution. We must carefully consider the provenance and limitations of synthetic scenarios, establish robust validation practices, and maintain transparency. Rather than leaning forward too quickly, a measured approach is needed to ensure these powerful new tools genuinely enhance, rather than obscure, our understanding of plausible climate futures.

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Competing Interests Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

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